

EFFECTIVENESS OF WORK CARRIED OUT IN COOPERATION WITH PRESCHOOL STUDENTS AND PARENTS

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Annotation This article requires students of preschool education to perform important tasks, which consists in searching for theoretical, methodological and practical foundations to determine and justify the content and structure of the process of preparation for cooperation with parents.

Key words: educational problems, politics, conflicts, fundamental change

The issue of professional training of future educators for pedagogical activity is one of the important issues in the focus of attention of scientists, researchers, methodologists and practitioners. Despite extensive research in this field, today the literature on the theory and methodology of preschool education and upbringing has not sufficiently revealed the essence of preparing educators for cooperation with children's parents, and the pedagogical conditions that ensure the effectiveness of this process have not been sufficiently defined. This is the basis for our conclusion that a unique model of professional training of students, which ensures the formation of the competence of family-pedagogical cooperation, has not been developed.

Pre-school education. This field, which is considered the primary link of the continuous education system, is extremely important in raising a healthy and well-rounded child and preparing him for school.

Although our past ancestors did not study the problems of youth psychology consistently and comprehensively, in a certain direction, based on a certain concept,

the works of scholars are valuable about the reflection, manifestation, development and changes of these situations. those who expressed their opinions. These can be found in four different sources: One of them is folk art, narratives, proverbs, proverbs and parables; The second one is in the advices and advices, stories written by special creative people dedicated to a specific person. The rise of the issue of cooperation between preschool education organization, school and higher education institution to the level of state policy points to the need for modern educators to have the necessary basic competencies in this field. Possessing such competencies serves as a practical expression of the social contract of the family, society and the state to fulfill educational requirements.

However, some spiritual and moral standards and traditions in the family are disappearing, conflicts between parents and children are increasing, parents are uneducated in solving educational problems, the family a number of negative events that indicate the crisis of the institution indicate that the theoretical and methodological base has not been developed in this regard. All this shows the need for professional training of students of preschool education in higher educational institutions for this process, theoretically and practically, taking into account the fundamental changes taking place in the family, education and society as a whole.

We think that it is appropriate to introduce the concept called "powers of family-pedagogical cooperation", which allows preschool education students to cooperate with parents, research and gain creative experience, reflects the readiness and ability of students for professional activities. Knowledge about cooperation is systematized and deepened by justifying and introducing its components. Cooperation in solving pedagogical problems and preventing conflict situations is a practical manifestation of the ideas of humanistic pedagogy. Therefore, first of all, it is necessary to use the didactic possibilities of teaching specialized subjects to equip students with knowledge about the essence and components of preparing them for cooperation with parents.

A special seminar on the topic "Forms and methods of formation of family-pedagogical cooperation competence: practical aspect", author's questionnaires and tests, development of recommendations for training sessions and organization of cooperation will give good results. It can be used in the development of training manuals for master's students, in the training system and directly in the educational process of preschool educational organizations.

Various district works, scientific works and new programs are being implemented on the effects of learning a foreign language on the personality development of preschool children. As our honorable president Sh.M. Mirziyayev noted, "Another issue that always comes to our mind is related to the manners, conduct, and, in a word, worldview of our youth. The psychological foundations of the child's personality have been studied by world and Uzbek psychologists and pedagogues for thousands of years.

In other words, the inconsistency of the preschool management system with new conditions is due not only to the rapid changes in the requirements of the external environment, but also to the inconsistency of the level of professional knowledge of the preschool management in the absence of a scientific approach to managing a preschool institution, non-compliance with the fundamental requirements of management science to the content of the management activities of the preschool educational institution and lack of knowledge of methods, ways to implement these fundamentals.

The obtained results of the strategic analysis of the external environment can be used as a basis for the formation of a number of strategic conclusions. For example, comparing the key success factors in the non-profit sector with the strengths and weaknesses of managing a preschool institution reveals that at present, the management of a preschool institution in our country does not allow creating the necessary conditions for ensuring the successful operation of preschool educational institutions.

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